

Novel tissue engineering methods for bile duct reconstruction

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Iatrogenic bile duct injuries following cholecystectomy for gallstone disease represent a serious and challenging surgical complication. Intraoperative bile duct injuries requiring its repair observed in 0.05–2.7% of patients, who underwent cholecystectomy due to cholelithiasis. Lots of patients require reconstructive bile duct surgery given that cholecystectomy is the second most common surgery in the abdominal region, and more than 1 mln operations are made all over the world per year. The standard surgery includes suturing of the duct with small intestine, but such a reconstruction can lead to liver abscess, biliary cirrhosis and increased risk of cholangiocarcinoma [1]. No one method was proposed as the best option for the repair and native reconstruction of common bile duct (Fig.1), though the use of bioengineered materials and methods is keeping an experimental surgery research.

Fig.1 Location of the Common Bile Duct (CBD) and schema of CBD's multilayer structure.

In early studies was theoretically analyzed of methods for creating a three-dimensional universal tissue-engineering graft of the common bile duct and consider the possibility of creating fragments of tissue engineered bile duct, which involves the use of tissue-engineering structures, consisting of a matrix of cells and signaling molecules [1,2]. Used electrospinning methods were prepared of several experimental samples for forming biocompatible tissue-engineered constructions of the bile duct using four polymers: polycaprolactone (PCL), a copolymer of D,L-lactide-co-glycolide of composition 75:25 (PDLGA), a copolymer of L-lactide with ϵ -caprolactone of composition 70:30 (PLC), and cellulose diacetate. The samples were two-layer structures having an impermeable to bile layer. Characteristics of PCL inner layer were the same for all samples. Determination of optimum parameters were based on the results of experiments on MTT assays with two standardized lines of stromal (3T3) and epithelial (MCF7) cells. Biodegradation kinetics test of experimental biocompatible samples was carried out in various mediums: water, phosphate buffer, Fenton reagent, bile, a nutrient solution with or without serum, as well as in the presence of eukaryotic cells [2]. Are supposed, the bile duct repair with the multilayer construction will contribute to formation of physiologically equivalents of tissue without any focuses of disease (Tab.1).

№	Causes of the diseases	Pathologies
1	Injures of the epithelial layer of cholangiocytes	Fibrosis, stenosis, biliary strictures; Cholangitis.
2	Injures of bile duct blood vessels	Ischemia; Stenosis, strictures; Infections.
3	Injures of bile duct innervation	Dyskinesia.

Tab.1 Impact of injures of multilayer structure components on tissue-specific bile duct pathologies.

Although the first surgery with the use of polymeric tube for its partial epithelialization during 3 weeks were carried out in 1913 by Propping [3], it was necessary to create the instrumentation tools for tissue engineering based on achievements of cell biology (immunohistochemistry, flow cytometry, induced pluripotency), microbiology (nucleic acid amplification from single cell, metagenome analysis), biotechnology (growth factors, transcription factors, gene therapy vectors) and biochemistry (electrospinning method). Actually, electrospinning is the most promising and technological method to obtaining fibrous and porous biocompatible materials [4]. In addition, state-of-the-art research tools for bioengineer-surgeon includes techniques with adequate physiological models from selecting animals to genetically-engineered humanizing mini-pigs. Was found the biomechanical properties of mini-pig bile ducts aged 7 to 10 months close to the same parameters in humans in early experimental studies on animals [5]. During the reconstruction of extrahepatic duct mini-pigs using a collagen matrix, functionalized by rhFGF, the formation of a complete monolayer CK19+ cells noted 8 weeks after surgery [6]. Use of a biodegradable copolymer of polylactic acid (PLA) and PCL (50:50), reinforced with polyglycolic acid fibers, in the reconstruction of the bile duct required 6 months for epithelium regeneration in the case of a full prosthesis [7], and 4 months using the patch (with size 20 mm x 10 mm) [8].

Studies on the biodegradation of specimens biocompatible in different mediums, particularly in the bile, showed the feasibility of further use as carcass material PCL, cellulose diacetate and PLC (retain their structural properties of more than 2 weeks). The study revealed the strength characteristics about the same ratio values of the longitudinal and transverse strength obtained on the scaffold of native and decellularized bile ducts, as well as the values of Young's modulus. As a result of screening using the MCF7 and 3T3 cell lines and methods using light microscopy and MTT assay revealed the most biologically suitable materials. Through the instrumentality of electrospinning copolymers of lactic acid were produced and been choosed the best samples of the materials for the tubular tissue-engineering bile duct graft development: PCL (inner layer) and PLC (outer layer) [2]. Thus, with the help of electrospinning copolymers of lactic acid were produced and been studied the best samples of the materials for formation of the tubular tissue-engineering graft with surfaced epithelialization and intra-layered vascularization.

Creating an artificial matrix for different cells types is a complex problem related to the selection of non-toxic polymer and method for material forming, activation exogenous extracellular matrix with specific properties, and long-term biological effects of ready-to-use cell-engineered graft. Conclusions about the usefulness of a particular polymer can be made only after the cell growth studies on scaffolds made of degradable biomaterials (electrospinning parameters influence the morphology of the material), and studies in model medium as well as *in vivo*. The work was supported by Ministry of Education and Science of the Russian Federation (grant No. 14.604.21.0133, ID RFMEFI60414X0133).

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